

SESQUITERPENES AND RELATED SUBSTANCES. PART VI.
SYNTHESIS OF A C₁₅-AZULENE*

BY PHANINDRA CHANDRA DUTTA

Synthesis of a C₁₅-azulene, isomeric with guaiazulene, has been described, but the position of the alkyl substituents in the azulene template could not be definitely established.

In a previous publication (Dutta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 885) the synthesis of the ketones (I, II) was described with the idea of developing methods for the important C₁₅-azulenes, which were obtained through dehydrogenation of some sesquiterpenes. The present investigation deals with the ketone (I) in an attempt to synthesise guaiazulene (III). However, before proceeding with the expensive ketone (I), some pilot experiments were carried out to fuse a cyclopentane ring to cycloheptanone derivatives. Preliminary studies consisted of the condensation of α-halogenated alicyclic ketones like bromoacetone or 3-bromobutan-2-one (IV) (Catch *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 274) with ethyl cycloheptanone carboxylate. Subsequent hydrolysis and ring-closure in one step might lead to the formation of (VIa, VIb).

The reaction resulted in the formation of the desired ketones but in a comparatively poor yield. The ketone (VIa) has been described recently (Islam and Raphael, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4086; 1955, 3152). In the case of (VIb), the condensation product (Vb) contained a trace of bromine which presumably arose from 3:3-dibromobutanone, which was produced simultaneously during the formation of the monobromoketone (IV). The removal of the former was found to be difficult through distillation because of very close boiling points, as contrasted to those of 1-bromo- or 1:3-dibromobutanone.

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Analysis of (IV) also indicated its contamination to the extent of about 5%. The ultraviolet absorption studies indicated the presence of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketonic system in (VI). Both the ketones yielded semicarbazones or phenylsemicarbazones which gradually turned yellowish during drying for analysis or on standing, a characteristic of some $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones (Simonsen *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 1576; Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1948, 81, 243). The wide difference in melting point of the semicarbazone of the ketone (VIa) from the recorded values might be explained due to this behaviour. The position of the methyl group in the ketone (VIb) has not been unequivocally established in view of the results obtained with the keto-ester (XIII) (*vide infra*). It is also difficult to rule out this uncertainty from ultraviolet studies alone for reasons to be discussed presently.

The next experiment, which was somewhat complimentary to the previous one, consisted of the condensation of bromocycloheptanone (VII) with ethyl methylacetoacetate. The condensation proceeded with 20% yield to furnish (VIII), but the removal of the carboxyl group proved to be an insurmountable difficulty due to extensive decomposition of the molecule under acidic or alkaline condition.

(VII)

(VIII)

Another approach to realise this objective may be schematically represented below:

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

On condensation of ethyl cycloheptanone carboxylate with ethyl α -bromopropionate, (IX) was readily obtained, which on alkaline hydrolysis afforded the acid (X). Attempt to convert the carboxyl group to acetyl (Wilds and Close, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3080) through the corresponding acid chloride failed and the product, so obtained, was found to be enol-lactone (XII). However, the elegant methods (Fujimoto, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 1856; Turner, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 580), which have been successfully exploited in recent years for the synthesis of unsaturated cyclic ketones, were not then available to be applied to this enol-lactone:

(XII)

Methylisopropylcycloheptanone (I) condensed with ethyl oxalate and the oxalo derivative, so obtained, was thermally degraded to (XIII) in presence of a trace of boric acid as a catalyst (Prelog *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 1586). The keto-ester (XIII) was condensed with ethyl α -bromopropionate to afford (XIV) which was converted into the acid (XV). Attempts to isolate the corresponding acid chloride or the enol-lactone also failed and the distilled product in the latter case smelt strongly of sulphur-containing impurities, evidently arising from thionyl chloride, used for the preparation of the acid chloride. The keto-ester (XIII) was again condensed with the bromo-ketone (IV). The crude condensation product was reduced with zinc and acetic acid to yield (XVI) and/or (XXI). On alkaline treatment, simultaneous hydrolysis and ring-closure took place leading to the formation of the ketone (XVII) in 60% yield. It exhibited the characteristic ultraviolet absorption, but there was a shift, although slight but significant, of the maximum towards the longer wave-length. This was hydrogenated to the saturated alcohol (XVIII), which on dehydration with phosphorus pentoxide yielded the hydrocarbon (XIX). On catalytic reduction, a saturated hydrocarbon (XX) was obtained, the infra-red spectra of which revealed considerable divergence in the finger-print region, when compared with that of perhydroguaiazulene.

(XVII: R=O)

(XIX)

(XX)

The unsaturated hydrocarbon (XIX) on dehydrogenation with palladium-charcoal catalyst (Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 2144; method 3) yielded a blue C_{15} -azulene. The trinitrobenzene complex showed a depression of m.p. of about 3° , when mixed with an authentic sample of the guaiazulene derivative (Plattner *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 32, 2452).

- (XIII): R = H ; R' = CO₂Et.
 (XIV): R = CO₂Et ; R' = CH.Me CO₂Et.
 (XV): R = H ; R' = CH.Me.CO₂H.
 (XVI): R = CO₂Et ; R' = CH.Me.CO.Me.
 (XXI): R = CO₂Et ; R' = CH₂COEt.

This has raised an important question regarding the location of the alkyl groups in the azulene template. It appeared highly improbable that the alkyl residues attached to the cycloheptane ring would exhibit any pronounced tendency to migration under these well-tried conditions of dehydrogenation. The remaining possibility might have arisen from the occurrence of the isomeric 3-methylketone along with the 5-methylketone

in (XVII), leading to the hypothesis that the C_{16} -azulene is mixture of *s*-guaiazulene and the isomeric 3:4-dimethyl-7-isopropylazulene because the migration of the methyl group in the cyclopentane ring also appears less likely during dehydrogenation. Attempts at establishing the non-homogeneity of the ketone (XVII) through the formation of a solid derivative like the semicarbazone, had to be abandoned. The derivative was not only comparatively unstable but also the parent ketone (I) was a mixture of diastereoisomers, as had been revealed in a previous publication (Dutta, *loc. cit.*). (XVII) was presumably formed from the isomeric condensation product (XXI). A slight bathochromic shift of the ultraviolet maximum may also indicate the presence of the isomeric 3-methylketone in (XVII), because the ultraviolet maximum ($232m\mu$) may be the composite of two different chromophores and, hence, occupy an intermediate position. This phenomenon has frequently been noticed in the field of the sesquiterpenes (Büchi and Rosenthan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 3860; Woodward and Yates, unpublished work on γ -metasantonin).

It may be mentioned here that Jacob and Sukh Dev (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 576) have published the synthesis of *s*-guaiazulene from the keto-ester (XIII) and the α -keto-ester of Simonsen *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 315) has also been utilised for the synthesis of (XIII) in their synthesis.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1-Carboethoxy-2-ketocycloheptyl)-acetone (Va).—An alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (2.5 g.) and alcohol (40 c.c.), was added slowly to a solution of ethyl cycloheptanone carboxylate (20 g.) and bromoacetone (16.7 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) with thorough cooling in a freezing mixture and stirring during addition. After the addition was complete, the cooling bath was removed and stirring was continued for 2 hours more. Next day it was refluxed on the water-bath for 1 hour and finally diluted with water. The product was extracted with ether and fractionally distilled. The fraction (9 g.) boiling at $115-18^\circ/0.35$ mm was collected. On redistillation it passed over at $119-22^\circ/0.4$ mm, yield 7.2 g. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 8.4. $C_{13}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 64.9; H, 8.3%).

1:2-cycloHeptano- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-4-one (VIa).—The above condensation product (1.5 g.) was dissolved in methanol (95 c.c.) and KOH (7 g.), dissolved in water (5 c.c.), was added. The solution was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 20 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralised with HCl (dil.). Methanol was removed on the water-bath and the residue taken up in ether. On distillation of the crude product, the desired product (0.3 g.) was collected at $88^\circ/0.3$ mm. λ_{max}^{alc} 228 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.8). (Found: C, 79.8; H, 9.4. $C_{10}H_{14}O$ requires C, 79.9; H, 9.4%).

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from methanol in thin flakes and the yellowish sample melted at $198-200^\circ$ (decomp.) (lit. m.p. $220-22^\circ$; 224°). (Found: C, 63.8; H, 8.3. $C_{11}H_{17}ON_2$ requires C, 63.7; H, 8.3%).

α -Bromocycloheptanone (VII).—cycloHeptanone (10 g.) in CCl_4 (20 c.c.) was mixed with N-bromosuccinimide (16 g.) and the mixture was refluxed for about half-an-hour on the water-bath. On cooling, the solution was filtered, the solvent removed and the bromoketone (5.2 g.) was obtained, b.p. $113-15^\circ/17$ mm. (Found: C, 43.8; H, 5.8. $C_7H_{11}OBr$ requires C, 44.0; H, 5.8%).

Ethyl 2-Ketocycloheptylmethylacetoacetate (VIII).—Potassium (1.5 g.) was dissolved in *tert.*-butyl alcohol (25 c.c.) and to this was added with cooling ethyl methylacetoacetate (9 g.). The above bromoketone (6.8 g.) was then added dropwise to the cooled mixture. After 2 hours at room temperature, the mixture was refluxed for one hour and this was worked up in the usual way. The desired condensation product (2 g.) passed over at 117-20°/0.15 mm. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 8.6. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 8.2%).

3(?)-(1'-*Carbethoxy-2'-ketocycloheptyl*)-*butan-2-one* (Vb).—To finely powdered sodium (0.9 g.) under benzene (20 c.c.) was added ethyl cycloheptanone carboxylate (15 g.). The clear solution, so obtained, was cooled, and to this a solution of bromoethylmethyl ketone (7 g.) in benzene (10 c.c.) was gradually added. Next day the mixture was refluxed for 3 hours. On working up the product, the following fractions were collected. Fraction (i): 8.5 g., b.p. 75-80°/0.05 mm. Fraction (ii): 4.5 g., b.p. 110-20°/0.05 mm.

The second fraction was refluxed for 3 hours with zinc dust (4 g.) in acetic acid (20 c.c.). On dilution with water, the oil was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution thoroughly washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally distilled. The desired product boiled at 108-10°/0.05 mm, yield 3.2 g. (Found: C, 66.3; H, 8.6. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 8.7%).

1:2-cycloHeptano-5 (?)-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-4-one (VIb).—The above ester (1.7 g.) was dissolved in methanol (150 c.c.) containing KOH (9 g.) and the solution was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 24 hours, when it turned slightly yellowish. On acidification with acetic acid (12 c.c.), methanol was removed on the water-bath and the residue, left in the flask, was extracted with ether. Finally the ketone (0.7 g.) was obtained boiling at 83-86°/0.1 mm; λ_{max}^{10} 229 m μ (log ϵ 4.0). (Found: C, 79.9; H, 9.8. $C_{11}H_{16}O$ requires C, 80.4; H, 9.8%).

The *phenylsemicarbazone* was prepared in the usual way, which on two crystallisations from alcohol melted at 183-85°. It turned yellowish on standing. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{23}ON_3$ requires C, 72.7; H, 7.8%).

Ethyl α -(1-Carbethoxy-2-ketocycloheptyl)-propionate (IX).—Sodium (1.2 g.) was finely powdered and taken under benzene (20 c.c.) and to this ethyl cycloheptanone carboxylate (14 g.) was added. To the clear solution, so obtained, was added ethyl α -bromopropionate (10 g.) in benzene (10 c.c.). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and finally refluxed for 4 hours. It was diluted with water and the product extracted with benzene. The required ester (12 g.) was obtained boiling at 120-24°/0.1 mm. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 63.3; H, 8.5%).

α -(2-Ketocycloheptyl)-*propionic Acid* (X).—The above condensation product (12 g.) was mixed with baryta (30 g.) in methanol (120 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed for 20 hours. After removal of methanol the residue was acidified and extracted with ether. The acid (4.5 g.) was isolated by distillation as a colorless viscous mass, b. p. at 128-30°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 8.6. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.1; H, 8.7%).

The *semicarbazone* on repeated crystallisations from aqueous alcohol melted at 160-61°. (Found: C, 54.6; H, 7.9. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires C, 54.7; H, 7.9%).

The *ethyl ester*, prepared through EtOH-H₂SO₄ method, boiled at 84°/0.1 mm. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 9.1. C₁₂H₂₀O₃ requires C, 67.8; H, 9.5%).

Enol-lactone (XII).—The keto-acid (X, 1.2 g.) was refluxed for half-an-hour with thionyl chloride (2 c.c.) in benzene (5 c.c.) after standing at room temperature for 2 hours. On removal of the low-boiling products, the yellowish residue passed over at 110-30°/0.3 mm as a reddish yellow liquid (0.4 g.). It was decolorised with charcoal in an ethereal solution. On redistillation, it distilled as a slightly yellowish liquid at 112-15°/0.2 mm. The colour deepened on standing for a few days. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 8.1. C₁₀H₁₄O₂ requires C, 72.2; H, 8.4%).

Ethyl 2-Methyl-5-isopropylcycloheptanone-7-carboxylate (XIII).—Sodium (1.5 g.) was dissolved in double distilled alcohol (25 c.c.) and the solution cooled in a freezing mixture. Ethyl oxalate (11 g.) was then added and the yellowish solution further cooled to -15°. Well-cooled methylisopropylcycloheptanone (8.4 g.) was added in two portions in the course of half-an-hour. The yellowish solution was allowed to stand at -10° for 2 days. It was then poured into ice and HCl (dil.) and the separated oil was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The residue left after removal of the solvent was slowly heated in vacuum (50 mm) after addition of boric acid (10 mg.), the temperature being raised from 130° to 170° in the course of 4 hours. Subsequently the temperature was raised to 185°, kept at that temperature for half-an-hour, the pressure being adjusted to 30 mm. A yellow oil (8 g.) distilled at 160°/19 mm. On redistillation, it passed over at 163-67°/19 mm or 105-107°/0.2 mm as a colorless oil, yield 7 g. Ferric chloride coloration in alcoholic solution was greenish blue. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 9.8. C₁₄H₂₄O₃ requires C, 69.9; H, 10.0%).

Ethyl α-(1-Carboethoxy-2-keto-3-methyl-6-isopropylcycloheptyl)-propionate (XIV).—The above ester (4.8 g.) was added to sodium dust (0.5 g.) under benzene (20 c.c.). To the clear solution was added with cooling ethyl α-bromopropionate (6 g.) and the product worked up as before. The condensation product (5 g.) distilled at 135-40°/0.08 mm. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 9.2. C₁₆H₂₂O₆ requires C, 67.0; H, 9.4%).

α-(2-Keto-8-methyl-6-isopropylcycloheptyl)-propionic Acid (XV).—The above condensation product (5 g.) was hydrolysed with baryta (15 g.) in aqueous methanol (150 c.c.) as described before. The gummy acid (2.4 g.) boiled at 134-36°/0.03 mm. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 9.9. C₁₄H₂₄O₃ requires C, 69.9; H, 10.0%).

3 (?)-1'-*Carboethoxy-2'-keto-3'-methyl-6'-isopropylcycloheptylbutan-2-one* (XVI).—The β-keto-ester (XIII, 12 g.) was added to sodium dust (0.8 g.) under benzene (20 c.c.) and to the resulting solution bromoethylmethyl ketone (6 g.) in benzene (10 c.c.) was added with cooling. It was worked up as before and the following fractions were collected:

Fraction (i): 7 g., b.p. 100-10°/0.03 mm.

Fraction (ii): 3.2 g., b.p. 115-35°/0.03 mm.

Fraction (iii): 1.5 g., b.p. 150-90°/0.03 mm.

Fraction (ii) was again refluxed for 3 hours with zinc dust (3 g.) in acetic acid (15 c.c.) as before. The diketone-ester (2 g.) boiled at 120-22°/0.03 mm. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 9.6. C₁₇H₂₆O₄ requires C, 69.6; H, 9.7%).

1:2-(3-Methyl-6'-isopropylcycloheptyl)-5 (?)-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentan-4-one (XVII).—The above condensation product (2 g.) was refluxed for 24 hours with KOH (12 g.) in methanol (200 c.c.). On working up the product, the desired ketone (1 g.) was obtained, b.p. 98-100°/0.02 mm; d_{20} , 0.986; n_D^{20} , 1.5087; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +32.3° ($c = 14.2$ mg./c.c. in alcohol); λ_{max}^{OH} 232 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1). (Found: C, 81.4; H, 10.8. $C_{15}H_{24}O$ requires C, 81.7; H, 10.9%).

1:2-(3'-Methyl-6'-isopropylcycloheptyl)-5(?)-methylcyclopentan-4-ol (XVIII).—The unsaturated ketone (1.5 g.) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of Raney nickel (4 g.) in rectified spirit (20 c.c.). It absorbed hydrogen (*ca.* 80 c.c. at 30°/758 mm) in 10 minutes and in two days the same amount was again taken up. The product was worked up and again reduced with sodium (0.5 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.). The alcohol (1.3 g.) distilled at 98-100°/0.2 mm as a viscous mass. (Found: C, 79.8; H, 12.5. $C_{15}H_{26}O$ requires C, 80.2; H, 12.6%).

1:2-(3'-Methyl-6'-isopropylcycloheptyl)-5 (?)-methylcyclopentene (XIX).—The alcohol (1.2 g.) was dissolved in petroleum ether (5 c.c.) and the solution was added to a suspension of P_2O_5 (4.5 g.) under the same solvent (20 c.c.). The mixture was shaken overnight. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and the residue was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The combined ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution and finally distilled. The hydrocarbon (0.8 g.) boiled at 77-79°/0.1 mm. (Found: C, 87.3; H, 12.7. $C_{15}H_{26}$ requires C, 87.3; H, 12.7%).

1:2-(3'-Methyl-6'-isopropylcycloheptyl)-5 (?)-methylcyclopentane (XX).—The unsaturated hydrocarbon (0.75 g.) was reduced in acetic acid (10 c.c.) in presence of platinum oxide catalyst. Reduction was complete in 15 minutes. The reduced product boiled at 117-20°/12 mm; d_{20} , 0.8779; n_D^{20} , 1.470; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +11.8° ($c = 11.7$ mg./c.c. in alcohol). (Found: C, 86.4; H, 13.4. $C_{15}H_{28}$ requires C, 86.4; H, 13.5%).

C_{15} -Azulene.—The unsaturated hydrocarbon (XIX, 1.1 g.) was dehydrogenated in an electrically heated tube over palladium catalyst (10 g. asbestos and 10 g. Pd/C, 10%), at 310-20° in the course of half-an-hour in a current of nitrogen. After the reaction was over, the catalyst was washed with petroleum ether. The crude product was dissolved in petroleum ether and chromatographed over alumina (15 g.). The first few fractions contained the colorless hydrocarbon, followed by an intensely blue solution which was collected. On evaporation of the solvent, a blue residue (15 mg.) was left behind. This was converted into a trinitrobenzene complex, which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 149°. This was dried at room temperature over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator for 4 days. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.1. $C_{21}H_{21}O_6N_3$ requires C, 61.3; H, 5.1%). The mixed melting point with an authentic sample of guaiazulene-trinitrobenzene complex (m.p. 150°) was 146-47°.

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